

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DOMAIN-DRIVEN DESIGN AND HEXAGONAL ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract

The thesis Development of an application based on hexagonal architecture and Domain-Driven Design focuses on elaborating and analyzing key concepts and principles of Domain-Driven Design and their implementation through hexagonal software development architecture.

The first part of the paper is grounded in the theoretical description of Domain-Driven Design concepts and Hexagonal Architecture, also known as "Ports and Adapters" and "Clean" architecture. The thesis discusses the essence and significance of creating modular applications through the precise separation of public abstractions and implementation details, by isolating domain logic from infrastructure and utilized technologies. Additionally, the thesis also emphasizes the importance of logically segregating code into modules, communication via APIs, and the subsequent decoupling of application components. This is noted for its impact on the capabilities for code testing, the introduction of new features, and the upgrading or replacement of existing technologies and business functionalities, as well as the potential for transforming modules into individual microservices.

The aim of the paper is to address key concepts of Domain-Driven Design and hexagonal architecture and to consider the importance of encapsulation, abstraction, and protection of business logic from the rest of the system as their primary tenets. The theoretical part of the paper allows for the identification of the advantages of hexagonal architecture over monolithic, single-module software architecture, as well as potential challenges in its implementation and maintenance.

Keywords: Domain-Driven Design, Ports and Adapters, Hexagonal Architecture, development, architecture, modules.

Introduction

The growth in size and the consequential complexity of business domains inevitably generates the necessity for adequate adaptation and redefinition of software, along with subsequent modifications of the business workflows without disruptions of the existing ones.

The growth of the codebase is directly correlated with the increase in software complexity, making it challenging to maintain the code in an organized and structured manner as per the initial design concepts. Throughout numerous development iterations, in the absence of strict adherence to architectural guidelines, maintaining separation of concerns and properly decoupling of classes and modules becomes increasingly challenging.

Addressing the previously mentioned issues, the foundation for elaborating on this work will be Domain-Driven Design and hexagonal architecture as approaches to software development with a significant degree of alignment between software artifacts and key business concepts and goals.

The paper "Domain-Driven Design and hexagonal architecture" pertains to the elaboration and analysis of key concepts and principles of Domain-Driven Design and their implementation through the hexagonal architecture.

The paper is based on a theoretical description of the concepts of DDD and hexagonal architecture, also known as "Ports and Adapters" and "clean" architecture. It explores the essence and significance of creating modular applications through the precise separation of public abstractions and implementation details, achieved by isolating domain logic from infrastructure and used technologies.

Furthermore, the significance of logically partitioning code into modules is underscored, emphasizing communication via APIs and the consequential decoupling of the application components. It highlights their impact on code testing capabilities, the introduction of new along with upgrading and replacing existing technologies and business functionalities, as well as the potential for transforming modules into individual microservices.

The goal of the paper is to delve into the key concepts of DDD and hexagonal architecture, exploring the significance of encapsulation, abstraction, and safeguarding business logic from the rest of the system as their primary tenets.

Additionally, the paper facilitates the identification of the advantages of the hexagonal architecture compared to monolithic and single-module software architecture, as well as potential challenges in its implementation and maintenance.

In the subsequent sections of the paper, the previously mentioned terminologies and their associated concepts will be thoroughly examined. Concretely, the paper will delve into DDD and hexagonal architecture, exploring their logical components, potential implementation scenarios, and offering a comprehensive mapping along with pertinent guidelines for integrating these models into a specific framework.

Domain-driven design

The rising complexity trend in contemporary business domains undoubtedly necessitates the need for adequate alignment of software, accompanied by subsequent modifications, while simultaneously preserving the integrity of the software and ensuring its compliance with current business processes.

The technical aspects of software, coupled with factors such as the absence or inadequately defined documentation, unclear and ambiguous goals, and resource constraints, may contribute to a negative impact on the potential complexity of the software. Furthermore, insufficient comprehension of the software, particularly as its complexity grows, may limit the possibilities for its secure adaptation and expansion.

To minimize risks and neutralize potential negative impacts stemming from the growth of software complexity, it is an imperative to exert effective control over complexity, involving appropriately defining software models and their corresponding architecture, while maintaining continuous monitoring and revision of the state and changes in its structure.

The key to successful complexity control lies in a robust model that transcends a superficial understanding of the domain by introducing a foundational structure (Santoso, 2018).

The term Domain-Driven Design was coined and established by Eric Evans in his seminal book "Domain-Driven Design: Tackling Complexity in Software" and it serves as a framework for systematically making design decisions in complex software domains.

The premises of the mentioned book are twofold, implying that the primary focus of most software projects should be on the domain and domain logic on one hand, and that complex domain design should be based on the domain on the other.

In line with the foregoing, DDD represents an approach to software development with a complex business domain that enables its efficient development, testing, maintenance, and modification, with its primary focus being the mapping of business concepts into software code by placing domain logic at the center of software development.

DDD pertains to the translation of business domain concepts into software artifacts (Penchikala, 2008) and is predominantly employed in applications where the domain model holds a pivotal role. In the realm of DDD, the domain model stands as the primary wellspring for designing and developing software that is intricately aligned with the business logic of the user domain, while concurrently downplaying the technical facets of the application (Hippchen, Giessler, Steinegger, Schneider & Abeck, 2017).

Additionally, DDD defines concepts and patterns that aid in the effective design of software in accordance with business requirements. It involves an approach to software development focused on various aspects of the domain – its structure, functions, logic, and language.

However, DDD does not prescribe a specific technology, methodology, or development approach; instead, it encompasses a set of concepts, principles, and best practices based on logically separating code into modules, isolating domain logic, and causally addressing technical and domain-related issues.

An architecture that separates technical concerns from domain concerns creates conditions for effectively adapting software to changes without undesired effects on unrelated parts of the code, enabling a cohesive design of individual components, making them simpler to interpret.

DDD provides a solid framework for designing and constructing business logic within the hexagonal architecture. The goal of DDD involves aligning software artifacts, such as design and documentation, with the business domain that the software addresses, resulting in the ability to swiftly respond to changing requirements driven by shifts in the business domain.

Additionally, with this development approach, the emphasis is placed on reducing technical debt, referring to the level of unnecessary complexity in the code. As well as this, elaborated concept can also encompass cruft, which represents the gap between the current code and the ideal setup of a software project (Vieira, 2022).

As previously mentioned, DDD fundamentally separates two spaces - the problem space and the solution space. The problem space abstractly models the primary business domain along with all its processes and dynamics. Within it, domain experts possess all the knowledge about these processes.

In contrast, the solution space corresponds to software artifacts and plays a role in the functioning and resolution of processes and issues in the problem space. When working in the solution space, to prevent misunderstandings in communication between developers and domain experts, a shared language is negotiated and adopted. This language represents more than just a glossary of terms, as it also defines the names of coding artifacts (e.g., class names), enabling interactive engineering sessions with domain experts.

However, adhering strictly and without further consideration to the aforementioned dictionary can, in many cases, lead to issues: What happens if different experts use the same lexicon to describe their domains (Vieira, 2022)?

By utilizing tools for tactical modeling, DDD also addresses the practical technical requirements of analysis and executive software development. These tools enable developers to create software that represents a tangible implementation of domain expert models, simultaneously being less prone to errors, scalable, and reliable. This approach generates a high likelihood of successful project completion within planned timelines (Vernon, 2012).

The effective implementation of DDD best practices relies on the existence of bounded contexts, a ubiquitous language, and related concepts (Vernon, 2012).

On the other hand, the inclination towards the functional classification of monoliths raises the question of how to identify stable, independent, and functional partitions along which decomposition is possible. DDD provides guidelines for the functional classification of domains, which, through the appropriate selection of subdomains and defining bounded contexts in software, also creates conditions for a sound technical decomposition. This technical decomposition is a prerequisite for breaking down the monolith and migrating to a microservices architecture (Lilienthal, 2019).

The decomposition of a system into modules or services is a challenging practical problem and a research question that has not been fully addressed yet. With the current trend towards microservices architecture, strategic DDD has become a popular technique for decomposing domains into so-called bounded contexts (Kapferer and Zimmermann, 2020).

The rise of complexity of monolithic software tends to reach a point where further improvements, upgrades, and maintenance become a significant burden. Single points of failure, characterized by potential breakpoints or bottlenecks resulting from the aforementioned challenges, encourage the fundamental engineering idea of dividing these monolithic applications into smaller services and eventually into microservices. This approach creates conditions for enhancing system performance and stability while simultaneously accelerating development cycles (Atanasov, 2017).

Overcoming the drawbacks related to the inconvenience of maintaining and upgrading new functionalities generated by monolithic architecture often entails and requires the reengineering of the current business system and its processes.

Specifically, and in line with the previously mentioned, the challenges of large and complex systems potentially find a solution in the migration of system components into separate entities – microservices. Their integration forms a distributed system of mutually independent individual services, with the potential for easier planning, development, upgrades, testing, and maintenance (Stojkov and Stojanov, 2021).

However, although microservices theoretically enable the single responsibility principle as one of the primary concepts of the SOLID architecture, the decomposition of existing services can lead to an accumulation of services and the creation of intricate relationships among them, increasing the overall system complexity (Mijušković, 2021).

The overarching issue with large software systems stems from their inherent complexity and the challenges associated with maintenance. In the early phases of development, the system's structure might not notably influence its performance and efficiency. Nevertheless, as the codebase anticipates growth in both scale and intricacy, the importance of sound architecture and structure becomes increasingly pivotal. Namely, a poorly defined and implemented architecture can result in difficulties comprehending the system.

A universal and pre-defined approach or strategy for transitioning from a monolithic to a microservices-based architecture does not exist. Nevertheless, examining common patterns observed in organizations that have successfully migrated their systems (Balalaie, Heydarnoori, Jamshidi, Tamburri, 2018) from monoliths to microservices can provide a valuable basis for understanding the strengths and weaknesses of implemented migration processes. This analysis can, in turn, aid in thoughtful consideration when making decisions about the planned migration for one's own system (Langurić and Zaki, 2022).

DDD provides several architectural patterns and templates, laying a solid foundation for creating "friendly" structured monoliths that can be transformed into microservices in a controlled manner. This generates conditions for a more comprehensive utilization of the benefits of both monolithic and microservices architectural concepts (Petrović, 2018).

Bounded context, one of the essential concepts in DDD, can be seen as a boundary that divides the domain model into zones, aiming to dissect and clarify potential ambiguities, uncertainties, and doubts that may arise during the development of domain-complex systems. Its purpose is to differentiate similar meanings without specific context in the domain model and clarify internal relationships within the defined context (Evans, 2004) (Newman, 2021).

However, when applying DDD to the development of microservices-based applications, several challenges may arise. Namely, DDD offers principles, patterns, activities, and examples for creating domain models as its key artifact. However, contrary to this, DDD does not provide a detailed and systematic development process for the application of these principles and patterns, nor does it categorize them within the field of software engineering (Hippchen, Giessler, Steingger, Schneider, Abeck, 2017).

In addition, there are no clear guidelines regarding the structuring of fundamental web application programming interfaces (web APIs), that, from a business perspective, hold strategic value. This underscores the need for them to be designed in a way that emphasizes quality (Iyer and Subramaniam, 2015).

DDD is a software development approach that emphasizes understanding the business domain and problem space, utilizing that understanding in the design and implementation of software. The primary idea of DDD is that software should reflect the real-world domain it models, and the language and concepts used in creating software should align with those employed by domain experts, ensuring the proper alignment of the software with the business needs.

In DDD, the domain takes center stage in the development process, and it becomes the responsibility of the development team to closely collaborate with domain experts. The goal is to acquire a comprehensive and detailed understanding of the domain and its requirements. This understanding is then utilized to create a shared language and model that is suitable for use by all stakeholders involved in the software development process.

The software segment containing business logic and addressing specific domain problems usually represents only a small part of the overall software system, yet its importance is disproportionate to its size.

Layered architecture supported by DDD emphasizes the grouping of related functionalities within an application into distinct layers with a vertical hierarchy among them. Each layer is functionally connected to another with a shared role or responsibility, while their mutual communication is explicit and loosely coupled.

The principles underlying layered architecture involve abstraction, reusability, clearly defined functional layers, loose coupling, high cohesion, and encapsulation (Chavan, Murugan & Chavan, 2015)

However, unlike typical variations of layered architecture with conceptual layers, DDD entails isolating the domain logic from infrastructure and user interface layers. Namely, by isolating and shielding the domain layer, surrounded by the application layer, the model is enabled to encapsulate significant business knowledge.

When delving into DDD, it's crucial to recognize the essentiality and importance of maintaining architectural neutrality within both strategic and technical domain models. However, some form of architecture is still required around and between each model.

The hexagonal, "Ports and Adapters," or "clean" architecture, which will be elaborated on in the next section, involves an architectural solution that fully supports the concepts of DDD while simultaneously creating conditions for facilitating the implementation of service-oriented, REST, and Event-Driven architectures (Vernon, 2012).

Moreover, beyond just delineating responsibilities, the application architecture must abstract the intricacies of a complex domain. This higher-level abstraction serves to shield the presentation layer from the impact of changes in domain logic.

In contrast to typical layered architectural models, DDD envisions the core of the architecture as the domain layer, housing all the logic related to business operations. Surrounding it is the application layer, which abstracts the lower-level domain details through a coarse-grained application programming interface (API) representing the business scenarios of the application. Specifically, domain logic and the application layer are isolated and shielded from the incidental complexities of clients, frameworks, and infrastructure concerns.

In DDD, defining model boundaries involves establishing clear and unambiguous distinctions between various parts of the system. By identifying independent parts of the domain and forming bounded contexts, clear responsibilities are assigned to each, creating a well-organized domain model, resulting in easier development, maintenance, and scalability of the system, composed of smaller, manageable components.

In the realm of DDD architecture, the monolithic approach poses a potential pitfall as it amalgamates all bounded contexts into a single entity without establishing distinct physical boundaries between them. This inevitably results in the blurring of distinct language

boundaries meant to represent individual contexts, consequently allowing the intrusion of the language from one context into another (Turis, 2019).

To circumvent the aforementioned issue, it is essential to maintain separate bounded contexts with minimal dependencies, ideally employing an anti-corruption layer or open host service, ensuring a clear segregation among contexts.

In addressing the mentioned issue, DDD introduces the concept of a bounded context, implying the definition of logical boundaries within which specific conditions and rules are consistently applied. Furthermore, within these boundaries, all terms, definitions, and concepts constitute a ubiquitous language.

By modeling the domain within the boundaries of a bounded context, it becomes a transition area from the problem space to the solution space (Santoso, 2018). Furthermore, by partitioning business domains into bounded contexts, the application becomes more maintainable, achieving good practices of loose coupling and reusability.

Additionally, maintaining the integrity of domain models within bounded contexts is crucial for developing robust and sustainable software systems. Bounded contexts defined in DDD emphasize explicit boundaries within the software system, where each defined subdomain has its own language, rules, and implementation requirements.

Therefore, maintaining and safeguarding the integrity of each model within the system and clearly defining the boundaries of their responsibilities in the code are crucial for developing a software system guided by DDD. By associating models with specific contexts, i.e., bounded contexts, defined based on the team's language and physical artifacts, conditions are created to sustain the system consistently and meaningfully, also being pivotal in managing complexity within the solution space.

Although the benefits of DDD are clear, its implementation generates certain technical challenges, primarily related to the time required to establish conditions for creating a successful software structure, synchronization of knowledge between domain and software experts, complexity in defining the domain model, and other aspects of implementing the considered architectural pattern.

Specifically, the challenges of implementing DDD are reflected in the time and effort required to establish a ubiquitous language and involve domain experts in the software development process, enabling their collaboration with software experts (Vernon, 2012). Challenges also arise from the complexity of creating and decomposing models, the bulkiness of the aggregate root, and the increased complexity of developing microservices-based software systems using DDD compared to monolithic architecture (Liu, 2021).

To overcome the challenges mentioned, careful consideration of the system architecture is required, along with the application of bounded contexts. Bounded contexts facilitate a clear definition of boundaries and model responsibilities, easing the understanding and maintenance of the system and fostering collaboration within the team.

Although agile methodologies offer effective management approaches for software development, providing frameworks for successful software solution implementation, their deficiency in supporting architecture construction and management (Dingsøyr & Moe, 2014) (Rost, Weitzel, Naab, Lenhart & Schmitt, 2014) can result in unnecessary redesign, architectural divergence, functional redundancy, and a subsequent escalation in system complexity. Undoubtedly, this is a challenge that deserves careful consideration (Mocker, 2009).

Overcoming the discussed challenges and successfully coordinating work, as well as developing scalable and reliable systems, requires proper management and architectural planning throughout the development process.

DDD fosters an iterative and incremental collaborative process for architecture development in an agile manner, leading to the advantages of its adoption and implementation. Specifically, a significant advantage of embracing and applying a development process based on DDD lies in the agile and iterative development approach it supports. DDD effectively addresses the existence of a software development architectural pattern while concurrently adhering to the principles of agile development.

On the other hand, DDD enables and enhances simpler communication among members of the development team. Thanks to the ubiquitous language, com-

munication between engineers and domain experts becomes significantly smoother. By establishing a common and ubiquitous language connected to the domain model early on, conditions are created for easier communication among development teams throughout the entire project lifecycle (Miteva, 2020).

Given that DDD is heavily grounded in the concepts of object-oriented analysis and design, nearly everything within the domain model is object-based, emphasizing aspects of modularity and encapsulation. This allows different components or even the entire system to be modified and improved on a regular, continuous basis, highlighting the flexibility that DDD ensures (Karam, 2018).

Hexagonal architecture

Layered architecture is one of the architectural solutions that supports the primary principles of software design. This architectural pattern represents the most general type of architecture for distributed systems, based on the idea of dividing the application into an arbitrary number of layers responsible for processing, data handling, and presentation, which can be separated physically and logically (Isailović, Stanković, Vasiljević & Ristić, 2021).

Despite the existence of diverse adaptations and interpretations of multilayered architecture to tailor the application structure to project requirements, the exclusive focus of DDD and hexagonal architecture will be on the hexagonal architecture as a representative of the considered architectural pattern.

Figure 1 – Hexagonal architecture with domain model in its center (Vernon, 2012)

Hexagonal architecture, also known as "Ports and Adapters" or "Clean" architecture, is an example of layered software design with a primary emphasis on separating business logic from infrastructure and the technologies used. The hexagonal architecture defines three building blocks – the user interface, business logic, and infrastructure (Storožev, 2021).

Hexagonal architecture, initially proposed in 2007 by Alistair Cockburn, a co-author of the Agile Manifesto, seeks to overcome the limitations of layered architecture. This architectural approach isolates the business logic and places it at the core (referred to as the core application in hexagonal architecture), exposing interfaces known as ports (Kolařík, 2019).

Cockburn's premise, as the originator of hexagonal architecture, underscores the application's versatility in being driven by users, programs, automated tests, and batch scripts. Importantly, it allows for independent development and testing, detached from the intricacies of infrastructure and specific technologies (Cockburn, 2005). Additionally, Cockburn emphasizes the need to separate the domain layer from the external world, including frameworks, user interfaces, and other technological and infrastructural details (Ilić, 2021).

Between the port and the external system lies an adapter that connects the business logic port to a specific technology (for example, a Data Access Object -

DAO - an abstract interface for a database). In this scenario, the core application is independent of the adapter, creating conditions for their easy interchangeability, such as substituting a generic Object Relational Mapping (ORM) for an optimized DAO (Kolařík, 2019). Furthermore, the architecture operates in a way that more than one adapter can be associated with a specific port (for example, the same business logic operation can be invoked either through a received message or a REST call) (Kolařík, 2019).

Figure 2 – Hexagonal architecture (Kolařík, 2019)

Although the term "hexagonal architecture" may sound complex, it actually represents a concisely defined design pattern where services, as components of business logic, do not communicate directly with external resources. Instead, services housed in the core of the application communicate with the layer of boundary interfaces, to which external services also connect to communicate with the interior of the application (Stojanović & Simović, 2019).

Hexagonal architecture fundamentally embodies a way of thinking, organizing, and modeling applications. It emphasizes an architectural pattern that involves centralizing the domain model at the core of the application and isolating it from technological code. This makes the software more resilient to changes, facilitates its continuous development, and allows the addition of new technologies without the need for significant refactoring (Vieira, 2022).

To prevent the leakage of technological details into the application core, protect business logic, and preserve its integrity, the concept of ports and adapters is used as a mediator between layers, where ports represent abstractions and adapters represent their concrete implementations (Callaway & Hunt, 2018).

Ports operate in two directions – inbound, managing calls to business logic from the external world by exposing core logic through a service interface, and outbound, defining how business logic communicates with the external world (Kolařík, 2019).

Adhering to hexagonal principles allows for structuring software in a way that reduces the effort needed

for understanding and maintaining code. Additionally, due to the specified architecture setup and adherence to the principles of dependency inversion, the code at the highest level is not dependent on the implementation of lower levels.

Hexagonal architecture involves an adapter layer that acts as a translation between the hexagon model and the external world in relation to it. Specifically, external systems communicate through ports with adapters, which then transform the request and forward it to the model.

Figure 2 illustrates that each type of client has its own adapter that transforms input protocols into inputs compatible with the application's internal API. Each side of the hexagon represents a different type of port, whether it is an input or an output. Three client requests arrive through the same type of input port (adapters A, B, and C), while one uses another type of port (adapter D). A possible assumption is that the first three use HTTP (browser, REST, SOAP, etc.), and the fourth uses AMQP (for example, RabbitMQ).

Hexagonal architecture does not explicitly define what a port signifies, making it a flexible concept. Any partitioning of ports involves receiving client requests and transforming their input by the adapter, after which it invokes an operation or sends an event to the application, transferring further control internally.

Additionally, a crucial note about the implementation of hexagonal architecture relates to its formation independently of the number of supported clients, relying solely on defined use cases. Therefore, any number

and type of clients can send requests through different ports, but each adapter delegates them to the application using the same API (Vernon, 2012).

The application receives client requests through its public API, and the boundaries of the application, defined by the internal hexagon, simultaneously represent the boundaries of the use case. In other words, use cases should be based on the functional requirements of the application, isolating them from the number of different clients or output mechanisms.

When the application receives a request through its API, it utilizes the domain model to fulfill all requests that involve executing business logic, meaning that the application's API is formed as a set of application services that are direct clients of the domain model (Vernon, 2012).

Large and complex applications require the existence of multiple entities, models, services, and code in general. Following the Separation of Concerns (SoC) principle involves separating the code into multiple parts based on the responsibilities they possess. As previously mentioned, this ensures the sustainability and smooth growth of the application, allowing for easier replacement of functionalities within the application.

Separating architecture using ports and adapters allows for easy modification and upgrades without touching the business logic. Additionally, achieving a multilayered architecture is desirable in the context of software maintenance and upgrades while simultaneously facilitating easier testing of the application without the need for connected elements (for example, the entire application can be tested in a black-box manner without the need for a database) (Kolafik, 2019).

Namely, the architecture setup based on separating domain logic from infrastructure and utilized technologies enables it to be independent of implementation details, making it suitable for testing without any dependencies on other systems. Specifically, business rules can be tested without the user interface, database, or any other external element. (Konuklar, 2020).

Moreover, developing the fundamental business logic independently of external interfaces simplifies the process of making system changes without concerns about impacting other interfaces and testing can be conducted seamlessly without the need for configuring or adjusting external interfaces (Słomka, 2020).

Hexagonal architecture and DDD

DDD and hexagonal architecture, also known as the Ports and Adapters architecture, are software design approaches aimed at creating software systems that are not only easy to comprehend, maintain, and evolve but are also more flexible, sustainable, and aligned with the specific needs of the business domain. These approaches complement each other, providing a powerful combination for building robust and adaptable software systems.

At a high, abstract level, hexagonal architecture is employed to separate the business logic of an application from the technical implementation details and its infrastructure. Concurrently, DDD offers a systematic approach to establishing a shared understanding of the business domain and its modeling through code.

In hexagonal architecture, the application core is encircled by a set of ports (interfaces) that define how to access the application core, along with a set of adapters connecting the application core to external systems like databases or user interfaces. The application core houses the system's business logic, independent of any specific technology or infrastructure.

When combining these two approaches, hexagonal architecture distinctly separates the business logic from the technical intricacies of its infrastructure, while DDD establishes a common language and comprehension of the business domain. This proves vital in shaping and guiding the design and implementation of the application core. Both design approaches are employed to craft software systems that align with business requirements. However, despite notable similarities, there are also key distinctions between the two approaches.

Indeed, DDD focuses on establishing a shared understanding of the business domain and leveraging it to guide software design. On the other hand, hexagonal architecture concentrates on separating and isolating the business logic of the application from its technical implementation details.

Related to previously stated, particularly within the realm of architectural layers and the dependencies generated among them, hexagonal architecture typically implies a clear distinction between the application core and the surrounding layers of ports and adapters. In contrast, DDD centers its focus on organizing code around the business domain, and the approaches to structuring the application itself can vary based on the specific needs of the domain.

Hexagonal architecture supports the application of DDD principles. Specifically, by separating the application logic from the input/output logic, domain objects can be developed independently of the user interface or database technology, promoting a clear separation of concerns (Słomka, 2020).

Additionally, in line with the concepts of DDD, hexagonal architecture advocates for test-driven development (TDD) by isolating the application logic from input/output logic and providing the conditions for easier writing of unit tests to verify functionality independently of other parts of the system.

In essence, hexagonal architecture not only encourages the utilization of DDD principles but also promotes test-driven development (TDD). By emphasizing these practices, the architecture seeks to establish a clear separation of responsibilities, fostering the creation of a more scalable and maintainable system, as highlighted by Słomka in 2020.

Implementation of hexagonal architecture

Current practices in implementing hexagonal architecture encompass variations in its application. While it can be employed at the system level, akin to a layered architecture, such an approach may diminish the primary advantages elucidated in the earlier sections of this paper.

A noteworthy example of best practices in hexagonal architecture involves crafting a hexagon within a bounded context, as depicted in the subsequent illustra-

tion. This implementation not only allows but also accentuates enhanced scalability of the application, drawing parallels with the scalability achieved through layers at the bounded context level in a layered architecture.

Ports will function as a communication channel between bounded contexts, while the role of a protective, anticorruption layer will be assumed by adapters,

generating conditions to preserve the integrity of the model within the bounded context and preventing the leakage and limitation of logic from one bounded context to another (Turis, 2019).

Figure 3 - Hexagonal architecture with one bounded context (Turis, 2019)

The organization of system components and the consideration of forming software architecture as a monolith or microservices are ongoing discussions within the software community. Historically, when issues such as expensive computing resources and limited network bandwidth influenced software architecture, there was a tendency to consolidate numerous responsibilities into a single software unit to optimize the utilization of available resources and prevent network overload.

In the process of structuring the system, the seemingly simplest solution involves consolidating everything into one place, resulting in a monolithic architecture. This architecture ensures that the software is designed to be self-contained and independent (Rouse, 2016).

The advantages of this pattern lie in its self-contained nature-facilitating rapid development, especially in the initial phase, and straightforward implementation since only one component is involved. Additionally, the entire development occurs in the same location, such as a single virtual machine, eliminating delays in system calls caused by network-related obstacles and consequently achieving higher throughput compared to distributed systems (Turis, 2019).

However, precisely because everything is in one place, this architecture introduces inherent drawbacks. The development of the system as a single entity increases the likelihood of generating interconnected and interdependent code. Additionally, the inability to horizontally scale the system due to its size poses significant challenges associated with monolithic architecture. Specifically, adding another machine to support an isolated part of the system becomes unfeasible as it

represents a bottleneck (Turis, 2019). The accumulation of responsibilities and the system's increasing complexity pose a serious risk of system failure, underscoring the importance and necessity of appropriately aggregating responsibilities in monolithic systems.

Monolithic architecture, despite occasional skepticism, can prove highly beneficial when applied judiciously, especially for smaller-scale systems that don't demand extensive scalability. Martin Fowler even advocates initiating application development with a monolithic architecture and transitioning to a more distributed solution only when the system's complexity surpasses the feasibility of remaining as a unified entity.

Reassessing monolithic software architecture and decomposing a sizable monolith into smaller, more manageable, and sometimes autonomous software components, often isolated within specific operational environments, yields substantial advantages in terms of the earlier-discussed separation of responsibilities. Nevertheless, alongside these benefits, it introduces considerations about managing complexity distributed across a network.

Hexagonal architecture can be applied to both monolithic and distributed systems. The hexagon contains elements responsible for describing the problems that the software addresses. Entities and value objects are key elements and fundamental concepts of DDD and hexagonal architecture. Entities represent things with an assignable identity, while value objects represent immutable components used to form the mentioned entities.

Discussion

DDD involves a holistic approach to software development with complex domain logic that requires a detailed and heterogeneous set of information sources,

knowledge, and expertise to ensure complete alignment of software with business priorities. Equally important, adopting a layered architecture guided by DDD results in technical design that is easier to maintain and upgrade, potentially extending the product's life cycle.

DDD, not being a "silver bullet" nor universal solution, is not suitable for straightforward software lacking a complex domain and without the need for an approach tailored to solving multiple problems. In contrast, DDD is not the right choice for a development approach in simple software without a complex domain where there is no need to implement an approach oriented towards solving multiple problems. However, contrary to the aforementioned, when designing and developing long-term software with significant domain complexity, where there are clear benefits from establishing a common language for information transfer in the development process, adopting DDD concepts may be of vital importance.

By adopting DDD, the development team gains the ability to construct a comprehensive overview of the project. This approach aids in coordinating software development aligned with business requirements, ensuring the creation of a comprehensive product without compromising its quality. Additionally, it assists in maintaining consistency throughout the entire design process, simplifying intricate issues and effectively bridging the gap between the business and technical facets of the development process.

The increase in interest and focus on the DDD theme results from the industry's shift towards developing microservices software architecture. Bounded contexts and the overall domain philosophy described in DDD are aimed at addressing the challenges of transitioning from outdated monoliths to microservices or constructing new platforms based on microservices architecture from scratch, leveraging the benefits of decentralization and loosely connected execution units.

Microservices architecture offers significant advantages over traditional architectures, ensuring scalability, accessibility, and flexibility. Although the hexagonal architecture was initially considered for monolithic applications, there is no doubt that the benefits of its use are well reflected in microservices architecture.

The entire discussion on the selection of software architecture becomes relevant due to the potential for generating conditions for the long-term maintenance and development of software. The hexagonal architecture is a design pattern for creating sustainable and adaptable software applications, ensuring a simultaneous reduction in complexity and the achievement of flexibility in the software system by separating the application logic from infrastructure and external dependencies.

However, despite being intended for complex software with detailed and intricate business logic, the hexagonal architecture can certainly ensure the long-term stability and scalability of applications with slightly less complexity. The proper implementation of the hexagonal architecture and related concepts from other development frameworks such as DDD, on which the mentioned architecture is based, can undoubtedly bring

significant value to the system and the enterprise as a whole.

Finally, the demonstration of communication between unrelated modules is ensured by the hexagonal architecture, providing enhanced ease of maintenance and the capability to change any part of the application without fear of regression in another part. The design and implementation of intricate software not only adhere to the architectural pattern proposed by DDD and the hexagonal architecture but also encapsulate the broader perspective inherent in the entire development paradigm.

References

1. Atanasov, M. (2017), Pucanje monolitnih aplikacija i potreba za mikroservisima, dostupno na: <https://startit.rs/pucanje-monolitnih-aplikacija-i-potreba-za-mikroservisima/>
2. Balalaie, Armin & Heydarnoori, Abbas & Jamshidi, Pooyan & Tamburri, Damian & Lynn, Theodore. (2018). *Microservices migration patterns*. Software: Practice and Experience. 48. 10.1002/spe.2608., dostupno na: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326601142_Microservices_migration_patterns
3. Callaway, J., & Hunt, C., (2018), *Practical Test-Driven Development using C# 7: Unleash the power of TDD by implementing real world examples under .NET environment and JavaScript*. Birmingham: Packt Publishing, dostupno na: <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/practical-test-driven-development/9781788398787/>
4. Cockburn, A., (2005), "Hexagonal architecture," [alistair.cockburn.us](http://alistair.cockburn.us/Hexagonal+architecture), dostupno na: <http://alistair.cockburn.us/Hexagonal+architecture>
5. Chavan, P. U, Murugan, M. and Chavan, P. P., "A Review on Software Architecture Styles with Layered Robotic Software Architecture," 2015 International Conference on Computing Communication Control and Automation, 2015, pp. 827-831, doi: 10.1109/ICCUBEA.2015.165., dostupno na: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/7155963>
6. Dingsøyr, T., Moe, N.B.: Towards principles of large-scale agile development. In: Dingsøyr, T., Moe, N.B., Tonelli, R., Counsell, S., Gencel, C., Petersen, K. (eds.) *XP 2014. LNBP*, vol. 199, pp. 1–8. Springer, Cham (2014), dostupno na: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14358-3_1
7. Evans, E., (2004), *Domain-Driven Design: Tackling Complexity in the Heart of Software*. Addison-Wesley, ISBN: 0321125215, dostupno na: <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/domain-driven-design-tackling/0321125215/>
8. Hippchen, B., Giessler, P., Steinegger, R., Schneider, M., Abeck, S., (2017), *Designing Microservice-Based Applications by Using a Domain-Driven Design Approach*. *International Journal on Advances in Software* (1942-2628). 10. 432 - 445., dostupno na: https://cm.tm.kit.edu/download/domain_driven_micro_service-architecture.pdf
9. Ilić, G., (2021), *Razvoj web aplikacije za pretraživanje jeftinih avionskih letova*, Sveučilište u Zagrebu, Fakultet organizacije i informatike Varaždin,

- dostupno na: <https://repozitorij.foi.unizg.hr/islandora/object/foi:6792/datastream/PDF/view>
10. Isailović, S., Stanković, M., Vasiljević, D., Ristić, L., (2021), Osnove distribuiranih sistema i distribuiranog programiranja, Metodologija stručnog i naučnog rada, Matematički fakultet, dostupno na: http://www.programskijezici.matf.bg.ac.rs/seminarski/teorija/03_DistribuiraniSistemi_IsailovicStankovicVasiljevicRistic.pdf
11. Iyer, B., Subramaniam, M., (2015), "The Strategic Value of APIs," dostupno na: <https://hbr.org/2015/01/the-strategic-value-of-apis>
12. Kapferer, S., Zimmermann, O. (2020). Domain-Driven Service Design. In: Dustdar, S. (eds) Service-Oriented Computing. SummerSOC 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1310. Springer, Cham, dostupno na: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64846-6_11
13. Karam, L. M., (2017), An Introduction to Domain Driven Design and Its Benefits, dostupno na: <https://dzone.com/articles/an-introduction-to-domain-driven-design-and-its-be>
14. Kolařík, V., (2019), Applying the Normalized Systems Theory on Microservice Architecture, dostupno na: <https://dspace.cvut.cz/bitstream/handle/10467/81234/F8-DP-2019-Kolarik-Vincenc-thesis.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
15. Konuklar, T., (2020), Hexagonal (Ports & Adapters) Architecture, dostupno na: <https://medium.com/idealo-tech-blog/hexagonal-ports-adapters-architecture-e3617bcf00a0>
16. Langurić, M., Zaki, L. (2022), Migrating monolithic system to domain-driven microservices Developing a generalized migration strategy for an architecture built on microservices, KTH School of Engineering Sciences in Chemistry, Biotechnology and Health, dostupno na: <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1666477/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
17. Lilienthal, C., (2019), From monoliths to modular architectures and microservices with DDD, dostupno na: <https://jaxlondon.com/blog/from-monoliths-to-modular-architectures-and-microservices-with-ddd/>
18. Liu, A., (2021), Domain Driven Design(DDD) and Microservice decomposition, dostupno na: <https://masteranyfield.com/2021/07/28/domain-driven-designddd-and-microservice-decomposition/>
19. Mijušković, V. (2021), Mainstream stručnjak odgovara na vaša pitanja o mikroservisima – šta treba znati pre upuštanja u ovu avanturu?, dostupno na: <https://www.netokracija.rs/mikroservisi-184922>
20. Miteva, S., (2020), The Concept of Domain-Driven Design Explained, dostupno na: <https://dev.to/microtica/the-concept-of-domain-driven-design-explained-1ccn>
21. Mocker, M., (2009), What is complex about 273 applications? untangling application architecture complexity in a case of European investment banking. In: 2009 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences HICSS 2009, pp. 1–14. IEEE
22. Newman, S. (2015). Building Microservices: Designing Fine-Grained Systems. O'Reilly Media. ISBN: 978-1491950357, dostupno na: <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/building-microservices-2nd/9781492034018/>
23. Penchikala, S., (2008), Domain Driven Design and Development In Practice, dostupno na: <https://www.infoq.com/articles/ddd-in-practice/>
24. Petrović, A. (2018), DDD i CQRS u fokusu septembarskog Java meetupa u Startit Centru Beograd, dostupno na: <https://startit.rs/java-meetup-u-beogradskom-startit-centru/>
25. Rost, D., Weitzel, B., Naab, M., Lenhart, T., Schmitt, H., (2015), Distilling best practices for agile development from architecture methodology. In: Weyns, D., Mirandola, R., Crnkovic, I. (eds.) ECSA 2015. LNCS, vol. 9278, pp. 259–267. Springer, Cham (2015), dostupno na: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23727-5>
26. Rouse, M, (2016). monolithic architecture, dostupno na: <https://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/monolithic-architecture>
27. Santoso, P.C., (2018), Breaking Complexity Using Domain-Driven Design, dostupno na: <https://www.mitrails.com/news-updates/breaking-complexity-using-domain-driven-design/>
28. Stojanović, S. & Simović, A., (2019), Serverless Applications with Node.js Using AWS Lambda and Claudia.js, Manning Publications, dostupno na: <https://www.manning.com/books/serverless-applications-with-node-js>
29. Stojkov, A., & Stojanov, Z. (2021). Pregled metoda za migraciju softverskih sistema na mikroservisnu arhitekturu. Journal of Engineering Management and Competitiveness (JEMC), 11(2), 152-162. <https://doi.org/10.5937/jemc2102152S>
30. Storožev, M., (2021), Exploration of Techniques to Visualise Code Quality, University of Tartu
31. Słomka, K. (2020), Using Hexagonal Architecture and DDD together for robust software design, dostupno na: <https://blog.slomka.pro/using-hexagonal-architecture-and-ddd-together-for-robust-software-design-d4b06a9beec3>
32. Turis, M., (2019), Domain-driven design with architectural patterns, Masaryk University, Faculty of Informatics, dostupno na: <https://is.muni.cz/th/azyz7/Thesis-Turis.pdf>
33. Vernon, V. (2012). Implementing domain-driven design. Place of publication not identified: Addison-Wesley Professional, dostupno na <https://media.oaipdf.com/pdf/152e8f22-51e8-4e04-86c9-1de1f6820e4b.pdf>
34. Vieira, D., (2022), Designing Hexagonal Architecture with Java : An architect's guide to building maintainable and change-tolerant applications with Java and Quarkus, Packt Publishing, ISBN-13 9781801816489, ISBN-10 1801816484